

FACTORS THAT INFLUENCED THE FORMATION OF BERDAQ WORLDVIEW

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Annotation: This article describes in detail the factors that influenced the formation of Berdaq's worldview, Berdaq's philosophical thoughts, and the fact that humanity also influenced the formation of Berdaq's philosophical views.

Key words: worldview, philosophical thoughts, Islamic environment, philosophical views.

Introduction: Berdaq's philosophical thoughts are developed in all his works in such a way that even we are forced to understand and generalize his philosophical thoughts. It is clear from his works that, like a real person of his time, he studied in Muslim educational institutions in a predominantly Islamic environment and followed the norms and rules approved by the society.

Literature analysis and methodology: Islamic ideology has educated a person in such a way that whoever believes in the existence of God and performs his actions becomes a true Muslim. God will certainly come to his servant who is offended by injustice and will always show his love for him in this servant. He will surely punish the person who hurt his servant.

And Berdaq agreed to this and considered it correct. He gave examples of vital social proofs. In his poem "Help us", the poet appealed to God. Berdaq's appeal to God justifies him in front of religious people. Because the poem shows that he has not forgotten God and that he will remember God in future situations through this poem. Berdaq's poem "Help us" is similar to the Rubaiyat of Omar Khayyam, the Persian poet. In his work "Help us", Berdaq showed other aspects of Islam to the people, the people. It is known that in his time Omar Khayyam was not left alone by mullahs and Islamists because of such works.

Berdaq did not only glorify man and describe his positive qualities in his works. He also created positive characters in his works. He tried to embody the qualities of a perfect person in his heroes. He harshly criticized the actions of unworthy persons who cite the name of man.

Results: Berdaq openly writes in many of his songs that in this period Karakalpak begs, fathers, and rich people used people instead of property, and that oppression increased to the extreme. Another characteristic feature of Berdak's works is his philanthropic, democratic, optimistic ideas. No matter how difficult and painful life he lived, no matter how persecuted he was, he did not give up the work of the people and did not lose hope for the future.

Berdaq devoted his whole life and energy to the service of the people. Berdak's dream was to give freedom and a bright day to the oppressed people. If we talk about the factors that influenced the formation of Berdak's philosophical views in this regard, we should not even remember the environment in which he was born and in which he lived.

Discussion: A prolific poet, despite being a Bakhshi, he put forward philosophical ideas in his poems and songs. Because we see his philosophical views in those poems and songs. As for the question of what kind of philosophy lies in it, a person who has read his poems knows. Believing in the existence of God in his philosophical idea emphasizes that one day God will punish oppressive officials and wealthy fathers.

Moreover, in the Holy Qur'an, it praises humanity for having familiarized its people with all the actions that they should perform in this world. Even then, ordinary people lived believing that their lives would improve and a prosperous life would come. In addition, Berdaq hated lying and people who oppressed ordinary people and made them suffer. For example: this idea is put forward in his poem "Better". Through this poem, he revealed all the deeds of such people, he even mentioned them by name and exposed their deeds to the common people. Such a feat is not possible for any person, but we can say that Berdak did this and achieved his goal.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it should be said that Berdaq showed that his philosophy is that of an ordinary person, and that mankind influenced the formation of his philosophical views. But not all people are the same, and among them there are people named above. We have to admit that this is a sad situation for this era. The poet took a philosophical approach to this situation and revealed his philosophy. We know from this that one of the factors that influenced the

formation of Berdaq's philosophical views was the fact that he was born in this period, lived in this period, was among this people, and saw and experienced these things with his own eyes.

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